

NATURE-BASED CLIMATE SCHOOL SHELTERS AND BEHAVIORAL DEVELOPMENT

The coolschools project

Hayat Bentouhami¹, Hanne Croons², Daphne Berden², Tim Nawrot² & Lidia Casas¹

¹ Social Epidemiology and Health Policy, University of Antwerp

² Centre for Environmental Sciences, Hasselt University

WHAT ARE WE INVESTIGATING?

In the Coolschools project we want to investigate the relationship between school yard green spaces (trees and other vegetation) and school surrounding green spaces with skills like memory and focus, behavior and well-being of children aged 10 to 11 years.

WHY IS THIS IMPORTANT?

Green spaces can help kids develop important skills like memory and focus, helping them succeed in school. Studies show that children who are exposed to green space show less emotional and behavioral difficulties. Adding nature to schools could be beneficial for children's behavior, however more research is needed.

HOW DID WE INVESTIGATE THIS?

In total 339 children from 22 schools participated in this study. We did measurements in all children. To assess behavioral problems, all children had to fill in a strengths and difficulties questionnaire. This is a screening questionnaire assessing symptoms of emotional problems, conduct problems, hyperactivity and/or inattention and peer relationship problems.

A 'GREENED' SCHOOLYARD IN PARIS

Prevalence of abnormal hyperactivity/inattention symptoms per category of school.

WHAT DID WE FIND?

The mean age of the children participating was 11.14 years. The prevalence of hyperactivity/inattention symptoms was lowest among children in low socioeconomic high green schools.

We found that in schools with high proportion of deprived children, vegetation, and the presence of trees, may help prevent behavioral problems in general, and particularly hyperactivity/inattention.

Want to know more about the Coolschools project? Visit www.coolschools.eu